

LINGUOPRAGMATICS AND ITS CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Alikhasanova Z. F.

Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute, Gulistan, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Research in the field of linguopragmatics has recently become increasingly relevant. Linguopragmatics as a field was formed in the 70s of the XX century. The formation of linguistic pragmatics is directly related to changes in the general orientation of foreign linguistics in the early 1970s, which are characterized as a transition from language learning, a formal system abstracted from the conditions of its use, to considering language as a means of communicative interaction carried out in a social context.*

Keywords: *linguopragmatics, communicative act, communicative unit, communicative goal, cognitive mechanism, cognitive processes, linguistic action, communicative and pragmatic aspect.*

INTRODUCTION

The period of the late 70s and early 80s, marked by increased attention to the human factor in language, was characterized by a sharp increase in interest in the communicative and pragmatic aspects of language use - in the structure of a communicative act, in the revision and expansion of the composition and functions of communicative units, in the adequacy of speech works to the communicative and activity needs and intentions of the speaker. The turn to the pragmatic aspects of the communicative act required, along with taking into account the achievements of traditional linguistic semantics, the inclusion in the field of language science of an extensive and still somewhat vague field of human knowledge – linguopragmatics. The rapidly progressing field of artificial intelligence studies has come to the fore; the communicative wave of research, responding to the trend towards intensification of interpersonal, interethnic and international contacts, required significant improvement in the practice of language teaching, especially in terms of the formation of active communicative speakers.

OBJECT OF THE RESEARCH AND METHODS

The object of linguopragmatics is the study of linguistic phenomena from the point of view of their use in real communicative situations. The main research method is a descriptive analysis of the key concepts of the science of linguopragmatics.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The formation of the science of pragmatics was stimulated by the ideas of J. Austin, J. Searle, G. Grice, Z. Wandler and others. This direction was also greatly influenced by the philosophy of language (Wittgenstein), which became an important sign of integrative processes in the humanities. "Linguopragmatics studies the use of language taking into account the age, gender, social status and professional characteristics of the communicants, as well as the specific conditions and goals of the speech act"[11] – science, which studies the ways of using language to achieve communicative goals, is naturally closely related to various areas and fields of knowledge, such as:

cognitive linguistics – linguopragmatics studies the use of language in specific communicative situations, as well as the influence of context, socio-cultural factors and

communication goals on the interpretation and understanding of linguistic expressions, deals with the use of language by an individual to achieve his goals, express his intentions, beliefs, emotions and their interaction with each other through language;

sociolinguistics – linguopragmatics explores the influence of social factors on the use of language in various contexts, which includes the study of differences in communication strategies depending on social status, age, gender and other factors;

psycholinguistics: Linguopragmatics also studies how psychological processes affect the understanding and use of language. This includes exploring the cognitive mechanisms underlying communication skills such as perception, memory, and attention.

Cross-cultural communication: linguopragmatics, among other things, studies differences in communication styles and norms between different cultures, which helps to understand which aspects of language and communication are universal and which depend on the cultural context.

Linguistic anthropology: linguopragmatics is concerned with the study of language and communication in the context of cultural and social practices that help to understand how language reflects and shapes cultural values and norms.

All these areas are closely interrelated and important for a complete understanding of the use of language for communication and the formation of perception of the world, and therefore a better understanding of the nature of human communication.

In general, many definitions of linguistic pragmatics can be grouped into groups:

- 1) interpretations in which the human factor is dominant;
- 2) definitions that emphasize the functional aspect of linguistic and pragmatic research, their contextual conditionality: the science of "language use", the science of "language in context";
- 3) definitions in which attention is focused on the study of the effect of linguistic communication in terms of the mutual influence of communicants in the communication process;
- 4) a number of definitions that emphasize the interpretative aspect of pragmatic studies of speech works appearing in various communicative contexts.

The main task of linguopragmatics is the study of language in its pragmatic function – as a means of influencing the behavior and consciousness of people in the process of communication. Special attention is paid to the factors that determine the choice of options for expressing a communicative intention; the conditions that determine the understanding of the communicative purpose of the statement. This problem is the subject of linguistic pragmatics.

Linguopragmatics includes a set of issues related to the speaking subject, the addressee, their interaction in communication, and the communication situation. The main postulate of science is considered to be the statement of J. Austin: "The word is the deed"[3].

Since the right to existence and maturity of any discipline are determined by the presence and degree of formation of its categorical apparatus, it becomes necessary to clarify a number of terms that are key concepts of such a field of linguistics as linguopragmatics. Such central concepts that organize the terminological apparatus of science include such terms as:

the addressee (speaker) – (from him. The sender is the sender of the text message. This concept appears in the work of M.M. Bakhtin – "a person initiating a communicative act and having the main purpose of attracting the addressee's attention to the object of speech"[4];

the addressee (listener) is a participant in communication to whom the text is addressed. The addressee (listener) is the third element of the rhetorical formula of speech (speaker - subject of speech - listener) and, according to Aristotle's definition, is the "ultimate goal" of speech [13];

intention (goal) – (Latin. *intentio* – "intention; aspiration") – the orientation of consciousness, thinking on any subject. Unlike desire, intention is understood as a planned plan of action. An intention – a communicative intention – can appear in the form of an idea to build an utterance in a particular style of speech, in a monological or dialogical form. A type of intention is a speech (communicative) intention – the intention to carry out a speech act. Intention can also mean an unconscious intention, literally "something that leads me from the inside to where I want to go"[14];

communication tactics and strategy. According to O. S. Issers, who develops T. A. van Dyck's approach, a communicative strategy should be understood as "a set of speech actions aimed at achieving a communicative goal"[6]. At the same time, the linguist connects this concept directly with the planning stage, when not only the strategy itself is determined, but also the tactics, means and techniques used are outlined in accordance with the general purpose of communication. This linguistic phenomenon, which determines the way to achieve the speaker's goal, involves "planning the process of speech communication depending on the specific conditions of communication and the personalities of the communicators, as well as the implementation of a communication plan" [8];

empathy is a conscious understanding of another person's inner world or emotional state. Accordingly, an empath is a person who has the ability to determine the mood of the interlocutor. Austrian psychoanalyst Sigmund Freud was one of the first to define the word "empathy", speaking about the need for a psychoanalyst to put himself in the patient's place in order to better understand him;

a speech act is a unit of communicative behavior that includes a linguistic action and its context, an act of communication in which certain statements are uttered in order to convey information, establish contact or influence the listener. The term was introduced into linguistic theory at the end of the 20th century by the Anglo-American philosopher John Austin, further developed by his student John Searle, and later expanded by the American linguist Heim Purcell;

pragmatic competence is "the ability to use language in accordance with certain communicative norms, goals and context. It includes knowledge and understanding of socio-cultural characteristics, norms and rules of communication within a certain language community"[2];

politeness – the use of language to express respect and goodwill to the interlocutor;

irony is the use of language to express the opposite meaning from what is being said explicitly. "Irony is understood, first of all, as a subtle hidden mockery, a form of expression of thought when a word or statement acquires a meaning in the context of speech that is opposite to the literal meaning or denies it [12];

sarcasm is a sarcastic mockery containing a negative assessment of a person, phenomenon or object – a statement with the opposite meaning, designed to downplay or emphasize the essence of a particular situation, fact, emotion.

context is a set of factors that surround a linguistic utterance and affect its understanding, for example, place, time, environment, participants in communication, etc.

a communication strategy is a way of using language to achieve a specific communication goal. "Communication strategy is the general planning of communication based on the current situation and the purpose of communication; such a plan can be focused on addressing the

emotional or rational side of the addressee, or influence him through a combination of rational and emotional arguments"[5];

contextual factors are factors that influence the understanding of linguistic utterances, such as place, time, environment, participants in communication, etc.;

an implicit contract is an implicit agreement between participants in communication regarding how they will behave and what goals they want to achieve;

contextual adaptation is the ability to adapt one's speech to various socio-cultural contexts and communication situations;

conventionality is the use of language in accordance with generally accepted norms and rules. Conventionality in linguistics is considered from the point of view of a system of pragmatic conventions governing dialogical interaction, and conventional norms, in turn, are "a set of rights and obligations of participants in communication within the framework of performing social and communicative roles"[9];

discourse is a set of related statements that form an integral communicative unit. Discourse is a polysemous term of text linguistics used by a number of authors in meanings that are almost homonymous. The most important of them are: 1) a coherent text; 2) the oral-colloquial form of the text; 3) dialogue; 4) a group of statements related in meaning; 5) a speech work as a given - written or oral"[10];

implicit and explicit acts of speech are different ways of expressing the intentions and goals of a communicative act.

rules of politeness are generally accepted norms of behavior in various social contexts that influence the choice of language expressions and communication style;

Contextual polysemy is a phenomenon where the same word can have different meanings depending on the context;

The principle of cooperation is the basic principle that underlies communication, and consists in the fact that communication participants should try to make their statements as clear and informative as possible for the interlocutor;

communicative competence is the ability to use language to achieve various communication goals, including persuasion, notification, request, i.e. a set of personal properties and capabilities, as well as linguistic and extra-linguistic knowledge and skills that ensure human communicative activity.

Communicative competence is considered as a structure consisting of five levels:

1) psychophysiological personality traits, which – from the general mental personality type (extroversion / introversion) to the device of the articulatory apparatus – largely determine a person's speech-thinking and proper communicative ability, help successful communication or make it difficult;

2) social characteristics and personality status (the communication process is influenced by a wide variety of social characteristics of a person: origin, gender, age, profession, belonging to a certain social group, the social role of the communicant);

3) the cultural fund of the individual – encyclopedic knowledge and assigned values (communication can be successful only if the fragments of the cultural fund of communicants actualized in the discourse largely coincide. Significant differences in the cultural foundations (background knowledge, presuppositions) of communication participants usually lead to the

formation of gaps, filling or compensating which will require additional efforts of the communicative leader);

4) linguistic competence of a person is a set of skills and abilities of a communicant, including:

a) the ability to express a given meaning in different ways (the ability to paraphrase);

b) the ability to extract meaning from what has been said and at the same time distinguish outwardly similar, but different in meaning statements (distinguishing homonymy) and find common meaning in outwardly different statements (possession of synonymy);

c) the ability to choose from a variety of means of expressing thought the one that best corresponds to the communication situation and expresses the personal characteristics of its participants with the greatest completeness (selective ability). In other words, it is a person's ability to successfully communicate based on his command of language and linguistic norms, on his ability to produce and understand texts of various types;

5) communication knowledge, skills and abilities of communication participants:

a) be able to effectively form a communication strategy;

b) be able to effectively use a variety of communication tactics;

c) be able to effectively represent yourself (or your company) as a participant in the communicative process, to possess communicative norms, establish and maintain communicative contact. Effectiveness refers to the correlation of verbal and non-verbal techniques with the goals and objectives of communication, a communicative perspective;

a communicative situation is the starting point of any speech action. This is a combination of circumstances that encourages a person to act verbally; generating a motive for utterance, which can develop into a need to perform a speech action. According to the definition of N. I. Formanovskaya, a communicative situation is "a complex of external conditions of communication and internal states of communicating, represented in speech behavior – utterance, discourse"[7].

linguistic action – the use of language to achieve a specific goal, for example, persuasion, notification, request, etc.;

context – a set of factors that surround a linguistic utterance and affect its understanding, for example, place, time, environment, participants in communication, etc.;

implicit and explicit meaning – the difference between what is also said explicitly what is implied or hidden in the statement.

CONCLUSION

Each natural language reflects a certain way of conceptualizing (perceiving and organizing) the world. Being the constitutive thinking ability of a person, language reflects the experience of human interaction with the environment and it is this, objectified in language in its entirety, that forms the linguistic picture of the world [1].

Thus, linguopragmatics is a branch of linguistics that studies linguistic phenomena from the point of view of their use in specific communicative situations. Unlike other areas of linguistics focused on the structure of language, linguopragmatics explores the use of linguistic means to achieve certain goals in communication, as well as differences in the use of language in different cultures and contexts. For example, in one culture certain forms of politeness may be mandatory, while in another they may be considered superfluous. The basic concepts of linguistic pragmatics play an important role in the analysis and understanding of people's linguistic behavior, their

application helps to improve communication skills, resolve conflicts and successfully interact with other people in the modern world, where communication plays a key role in all spheres of life. Unlike other areas of linguistics focused on the structure of language, linguopragmatics explores the use of linguistic means to achieve certain goals in communication, as well as differences in the use of language in different cultures and contexts.

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